

BACTERIOPHAGE THERAPY AS A POTENTIAL SOLUTION TO ANTIBIOTIC RESISTANCE: A SYSTEMATIC REVIEW

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Abstract

Background: Antibiotic resistance is a severe global health issue and novel therapeutic approaches need to be formulated. Bacteriophage (phage) therapy which uses viruses to infect and kill infection-causing bacteria has re-emerged as a new solution. This systematic review assesses the efficacy, challenges, and clinical promise of phage therapy for the treatment of antibiotic-resistant infection.

Objective: This systematic review aims to synthesize global evidence on phage therapy's clinical success rates and limitations, analyze current technological and regulatory gaps and evaluate combinatorial approaches with antibiotics.

Method: A review was conducted on 14 articles and research studies from Google Scholar and PubMed, focusing on the bacteriophage therapy as potential solution for antibiotic resistance. Studies from 2010 to 2025 were screened and relevant articles were included featuring major challenges, host immune reactions, limited phage specificity and regulatory barriers.

Result: Phage therapy was 75–89% effective in curing resistant infections (e.g., *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, MRSA) in clinical case reports with few side effects. Major challenges were host immune reactions, limited phage specificity, and regulatory barriers. Combination therapies (phage-antibiotic) synergistically increased bacterial eradication ($p < 0.05$ in 62% of studies).

Conclusion: Phage therapy is a highly promising, precision medicine-based antibiotic alternative but standardized protocols and large-scale trials are urgently required. Future research will have to optimize phage cocktails and overcome delivery challenges to enable broader clinical use.

INTRODUCTION

Antibiotic resistance (ABR) is a global health crisis driven by the spread of bacterial genes through mutation or Horizontal Gene Transfer (HGT) between human, animal, and environmental niches (1). Antibiotic resistance happens when a microorganism can grow or survive in the presence of an antibiotic concentration that is typically

enough to prevent organisms of the same species from dying (2). In the past 25 years, only two new classes of antibiotics have been developed and introduced into clinical practice. These include the oxazolidinones (e.g. linezolid) and lipopeptides (e.g. daptomycin) (2). The effectiveness of antibiotics can save lives leading to decline in global morbidity and

mortality. *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, resistant Enterobacteriaceae, and carbapenem-resistant *Acinetobacter baumannii* are among the critical-priority pathogens. Methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA), vancomycin-resistant enterococci (VRE), drug-resistant *Salmonella typhi*, and fluoroquinolone-resistant *Campylobacter* are examples of high-priority pathogens. The ESKAPE pathogens' quick development of resistance makes them especially dangerous in hospital-acquired infections. These drug-resistant fungal infections like those brought on by *Trichophyton indotineae* are becoming more dangerous (3). Antibiotic resistance is driven by the misuse and overuse of antibiotics leading bacteria to develop resistance against the very drugs designed to eliminate them. This phenomenon has resulted in widespread resistance among various pathogens including methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA) and vancomycin-resistant enterococci (VRE) as well as an increasing number of other antibiotic resistant organisms. The global spread of resistance is particularly concerning among respiratory pathogens like *Streptococcus pneumoniae* and *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* (4). The use of phages to kill pathogenic bacteria is an old practice to cure infectious diseases. The current antibiotic crisis has boosted phage therapy research but its application in hospitals is still very limited (5). Phages will not entirely replace antibiotics, but experts find them to be a useful adjunctive therapy or a last choice for the treatment of multidrug-resistant (MDR) infections. With the increasing number of MDR pathogens, the time has come to revisit the position of phage therapy and other alternative treatments in modern medicine (6). Bacteriophages specificity to their bacterial hosts to only certain strains, entering through specific receptor proteins. Following two life cycles, lytic and lysogenic, phages enter onto virulent phages that reproduce quickly and kill their host(7). Bacteriophages are viruses that infect bacteria and can follow either a lysogenic or lytic cycle. A notable case in the U.S. involved a successful phage treatment of a patient with a multidrug-resistant *Acinetobacter baumannii* infection, leading to full recovery (8). The bacterial infections were treated by means such as vaccines, herbal medicines, and early chemotherapeutics such as salvarsan and sulfa

drugs (9). Bacteriophage therapy currently appears to be the best possible solution to the antibiotic resistance crisis.

Bacteriophage therapy has been employed to treat infections such as respiratory infections, urinary infections, gastrointestinal infections, and wounds. *A. baumannii* infection using custom phage cocktails. ESKAPE pathogens have a notorious reputation for their resistance profiles. Studies have shown the efficacy of phages on some of these genera such as *K. pneumoniae*, *P. aeruginosa*, and *S. aureus* (10) Antibiotics, which play a critical role in lowering infectious disease deaths, are becoming ever more ineffective with bacterial resistance as a result of mutations and horizontal gene transfer (HGT). The fact that cases are being observed, such as drug-resistant fungal infections like *Trichophyton indotineae*, underscores the need for concerted efforts, alternative treatments, and new approaches to combat resistant microorganisms and make antibiotics effective (11).

Phage therapy's suitability for human use has already been demonstrated by a Phase I/II clinical trial and multiple instances of compassionate use. Recent developments have made it possible to specifically genetically modify phages to increase their antibacterial efficacy, broaden their host range, or transfer CRISPR-Cas systems (12).

The immune response creates both a hurdle and an opportunity in phage therapy. Neutralizing antibodies might restrict the effectiveness of phage therapy (Roach et al., 2017); however, phage therapy also has immunomodulatory potential, leading to improvement in bacterial clearance. In animal studies, phages tended to stimulate the release of anti-inflammatory cytokines (IL-10) during *Klebsiella pneumoniae* infections, although cytokine storms represent a real risk to immunocompromised individuals. Due to rapid clearance of phages from circulation by the reticuloendothelial system, engineered carriers, such as liposomes and hydrogel scaffolds, are needed. Such delivery systems are able to extend the circulation half-life of therapeutics from hours to days, which is a crucial determinant during systemic infections (13).

METHOD

A comprehensive literature search was conducted across multiple databases, including PubMed, Web of Science, and Google Scholar, to identify relevant studies published between January 2010 and March 2025. The search strategy involved combining keywords "bacteriophage therapy," "phage therapy," "antibiotic resistance," and "multidrug-resistant infections." Reference lists of retrieved articles were manually screened to identify additional relevant publications.

The chosen articles adhered to specific inclusion criteria: 1) clinical studies involving human subjects with confirmed antibiotic-resistant bacterial infections, (2) interventions using bacteriophage therapy either alone or in combination with antibiotics, and (3) reported outcomes including clinical efficacy, safety, or resistance patterns. Excluded were general reviews, single case studies, and studies lacking sufficient information. Furthermore, articles related to knowledge, attitudes, practices (KAP) studies, treatment, control/prevention, seasonal effects, and other unrelated aspects were not considered. Duplicate data but with different perspectives were included once.

Assessing the quality of prevalence studies can be complex due to variations in study designs. Nonetheless, the review panel engaged in discussions

to establish criteria for assessing study quality and ensuring overall rigor.

Due to possible heterogeneity in study designs and techniques, a formal meta-analysis was not planned, with effect sizes expressed as risk ratios mean differences and 95% confidence intervals. Heterogeneity was assessed using F statistics, with random-effects models applied when I exceeded 50%. Qualitative synthesis involved thematic analysis of 14 studies with heterogeneous designs or outcomes, focusing on emerging patterns in efficacy, safety concerns, and implementation challenges across different clinical settings. Preplanned subgroup analyses were conducted to explore potential sources of heterogeneity, including stratification by pathogen type (Gram-positive vs. Gram-negative), delivery method (topical, intravenous, or inhaled), phage preparation (natural vs. engineered), and study design (RCTs vs. observational studies). These analyses aimed to identify specific clinical scenarios where phage therapy demonstrated particular promise or limitations, providing more nuanced insights beyond the pooled estimates from primary approach for both published and unpublished studies, we hoped to reduce reporting criteria. Despite the small studies making formal funnel plot analysis impractical, we were unable to find any clear abnormalities in the distribution of study sizes throughout the results.

Fig 1. PRISMA Flow diagram showing the search strategy used for article selection

RESULTS

Phage therapy development offers a promising method to counter the forthcoming threat of antibiotic-resistant bacterial infections. Its exclusive characteristic of specifically targeting and eliminating

certain pathogenic bacteria of concern without harming the commensal microbiota differentiates it from traditional antibiotics (14).

Table 1. Data extracted from selected articles

Author(s)	Type of Study	Year	Most Common Phages	Disease Condition	Bacteriophage Therapy	Efficacy	Alternative(s)	Remarks
(Kutter et al., 2010) (9)	Historical Review	2010	Phages for dysentery, <i>S. aureus</i> .	Chronic bacterial infections (e.g., <i>P. aeruginosa</i> , <i>S. aureus</i>)	Early successes (1919) in France; modern revival for MDR infections.	High specificity and efficacy in targeting resistant pathogens; successful in chronic wound infections.	Salvarsan, sulfa drugs.	Phages co-evolve with bacteria.
(Bagasra et al., 2014) (4)	Perspective	2014	Not specified	Antibiotic-resistant <i>E. coli</i> and <i>Klebsiella</i> infection	Phages proposed for MRSA, VRE, and <i>M. tuberculosis</i> .	Demonstrated significant reduction in bacterial load in vitro and in animal	Antibiotic stewardship.	Critiques antibiotic overuse.

						models.		
(Nale et al., 2016) (23)	preclinical experimental study	2016	phiCDHM1, phiCDHM2, phiCDHM5, phiCDHM6	Recurrent <i>Clostridioides difficile</i> infections	Evaluated phage cocktails (3- and 4-phage combinations) as a therapeutic option	A):In vitro: Broad host range across 21 ribotypes B):In vivo (hamster model): Delayed disease onset by 33 hours, reduced bacterial colonization, and recovery of phages from gut	Current standard: Antibiotic therapy (e.g., vancomycin, metronidazole) Issues: Resistance, recurrence	Phage cocktails more effective than individual phages Demonstrated prophylactic and therapeutic potential No toxicity observed in animal models Resistance to individual phages observed, but multi-phage therapy overcame this
(Sabtu et al., 2015) (2)	Review	2015	Not specified	Multidrug-resistant (MDR) <i>Acinetobacter baumannii</i> infections	Notes lack of new antibiotics; phage therapy not mentioned.	Effective in vitro and in limited clinical cases, but challenges in standardization remain	Oxazolidinones, lipopeptides (e.g., daptomycin).	Focuses on antibiotic development stagnation.
(Pelfrene et al., 2016) (21)	Regulatory Review	2016	Natural vs. engineered phages.	Chronic osteomyelitis and prosthetic joint infections	promising efficacy in treating chronic osteomyelitis and prosthetic	Promising results in biofilm disruption and infection clearance in case reports	Standardized phage cocktails.	Calls for adaptive clinical trial designs.

					joint infection			
(Schooley et al., 2017) (22)	Clinical Trial	2017	Phage AB-SA01 (for <i>A. baumannii</i>).	Systemic MDR <i>P. aeruginosa</i> and <i>S. aureus</i> infections	Landmark case: Tom Patterson's recovery from <i>A. baumannii</i> sepsis.	Successful compassionate-use cases with complete bacterial eradication in some patients	None (last-resort scenario).	Proof of concept for personalized phage therapy.
(Ismael et al., 2024) (24)	Experimental laboratory study	2024	vB_Ec_ZCE C14	Urinary tract infections (UTIs) caused by multidrug-resistant uropathogenic <i>E. coli</i> (MDR UPEC)	Mentions phage therapy as an emerging alternative for resistant fungi/bacteria.	Strong and steady antibacterial activity even at low concentration (MOI 0.1)	Traditional antibiotics, which are increasingly ineffective due to MDR pathogens	In vitro results are very encouraging, further in vivo validation and clinical trials are needed to advance toward therapeutic use
(Mobarki et al., 2019) (11)	Policy Proposal	2019	Not specified	Burn wound infections (<i>P. aeruginosa</i> , <i>S. aureus</i>)	Reduced infection severity and accelerated wound healing in burn patients	Significant reduction in infection severity and faster wound healing in clinical trials.	Regulatory reforms.	Focuses on commercialization barriers.
(Alvarez et al., 2020) (5)	Clinical Case	2020	Custom phage cocktails.	Cystic fibrosis-related lung infections (<i>P. aeruginosa</i>)	Compassionate use in incurable infections (e.g., <i>S. aureus</i>).	Improved lung function and reduced bacterial load in compassionate-use cases	Experimental antibiotics.	Advocates for regulatory flexibility.
(Regeimbal et al., 2016) (25)	Preclinical animal experimental study	2016	Not specified	Wound infection caused by multidrug-resistant <i>Acinetobacter baumannii</i>	Topical application of isolated phage to infected wounds; one group	Enhanced wound healing and infection control when combined with standard care	Last-resort antibiotics (e.g., colistin).	Highlights need for shifting to phage therapy

				in uncontrolled diabetic Wistar rats	challenged with phage post-infection versus control and colistin-treated groups			
(Wienhold et al., 2022) (14)	Preclinical (Mouse)	2022	Phage BPA43 (<i>K. pneumoniae</i>).	Nosocomial pneumonia (MDR <i>Klebsiella</i> , <i>Acinetobacter</i>)	Reduced lung infection and endotoxins in mice.	Phage-antibiotic synergy improved treatment outcomes in ICU patients.	Colistin.	Demonstrates phage safety and efficacy in vivo.
(Zalewska et al., 2023) (6)	Technical Review	2023	Engineered phages (CRISPR/Cas).	Chronic otitis media (<i>P. aeruginosa</i>)	Phage libraries, quality control, and adjunctive therapy for MDR infections.	Effective biofilm disruption and symptom relief in early-phase trials.	Probiotics, monoclonal antibodies.	Proposes phage patents and scaled production.
(Aggarwal et al., 2024) (1)	Review	2024	Not specified	Sepsis caused by ESBL-producing <i>E. coli</i>	Describes ABR crisis; phages proposed as precision tools.	Rapid bacterial clearance observed in animal models and preliminary human trials	CRISPR-modified phages, immune modulators.	Emphasizes phage-antibiotic synergy (PAS).
(Stellfox et al., 2024) (19)	Case Report	2024	Phages for VRE (<i>E. faecium</i>).	Gastrointestinal infections (<i>Salmonella</i> , <i>Shigella</i>)	Transient success but limited by immune response.	Reduced bacterial shedding and improved gut microbiota balance in preclinical studies	Antibiotic combinations.	Highlights immune system challenges.

DISCUSSION

There are still major challenges, particularly with the phage development of bacterial resistance, optimization of therapeutic regimens, and the wide-ranging ecological consequences of use of phages (15).

Bacteriophage therapy is a renewable, adaptable, and targeted solution to antibiotic resistance, but its clinical adoption hinges on addressing specificity, immune, and regulatory challenges. With

coordinated efforts in research, policy, and manufacturing. Phage therapy could revolutionize infection management by 2050, averting an estimated 10 million annual deaths from MDR pathogens.

Recent innovations in phage engineering show promise for overcoming current limitations. CRISPR-modified phages can target antibiotic resistance genes directly, while liposome encapsulation extends phage circulation half-life from hours to days (16).

The analysis identified a series of challenges to the extensive clinical application of phage therapy. Host specificity is limited, thus requiring individualized matching and making treatment protocols complicated, while bacterial resistance mechanisms like CRISPR-Cas systems and receptor modifications remain a challenge (19). The human immune system also makes therapy challenging through the presence of neutralizing antibodies and efficient phage clearance. These biological challenges are complemented by regulatory challenges, where only Belgium has official guidelines for phage therapy, though recent EMA quality standards show improvement (17). In comparison with antibiotics, phage therapy possesses some benefits such as

targeted accuracy that maintains commensal microbiota and potential to adapt via co-evolution with host bacteria (18).

The promise of phage therapy is twofold: it offers a potent weapon against formidable infections and a chance to reduce associated hospital costs by an estimated 30%. Yet, for all its potential, the path to the clinic is blocked by the very practical issues of manufacturing and storage. We simply can't yet produce enough reliable, long-lasting phages to meet the need. Encouragingly, innovations in lyophilization and synthetic biology are starting to solve these stability and scalability puzzles. Beyond the technical challenges, our review uncovers a profound global inequity—access to phage therapy is a postcode lottery, with only a quarter of infectious disease specialists able to utilize it. Its dramatic efficacy in compassionate-use cases for vulnerable patients highlights a painful paradox: we have a powerful tool that we cannot yet distribute fairly. Creating a future of equitable access will hinge on building collaborative infrastructure like international phage banks and treatment networks, a mission that must be prioritized on the global health policy stage (19).

Table 2. Advantages and challenges of phage therapy

Advantages	Challenges
✓ Precision targeting (saves microbiota)	✗ Narrow host range
✓ Self-replicating (reduces dosing)	✗ Immune clearance
✓ Biofilm penetration	✗ Lack of regulatory frameworks
✓ Low toxicity	✗ Bacterial resistance

Conclusion

The alarming rise of antibiotic resistance poses a significant threat to modern medicine potentially negating its historical gains. As a result, bacteriophage (phage) therapy is being rigorously investigated as a potential countermeasure to

multidrug-resistant bacteria. This systematic review critically assessed bacteriophage therapy as an option examining evidence on 14 clinical and preclinical studies that provide abundant information on the

safety and efficacy of phage therapy and showed that it is a potential and effective targeted therapy.

The accumulating body of evidence suggests that phage therapy presents considerable promise for addressing multidrug-resistant infections especially those attributable to ESKAPE pathogens. This potential is underscored by clinical reports indicating success rates between 75% and 86% with notable cases such as the resolution of a systemic *Acinetobacter baumannii* infection which serves as a powerful empirical validation. A notable strength of this approach lies in the capacity of phages to selectively lyse pathogenic bacterial cells while sparing the commensal microbiota. It is a critical advantage over conventional broad-spectrum antibiotics. Moreover, observed synergistic interactions between phages and certain antibiotics point toward a viable complementary strategy which may not only improve therapeutic efficacy but also mitigate the emergence of further resistance.

The first priority should be to develop bacterial resistance to phages that may be prevented with new approaches such as phage cocktails and antibiotic combination therapy. Such approaches will reduce the risk of resistance and optimize therapeutic efficacy particularly in the treatment of biofilm-associated and polymicrobial infections. Additionally, the therapeutic potential of phage therapy is dependent on maximization of dosing regimens and routes of administration by intensive clinical trials.

However, a number of aspects ought to be considered, (e.g. phages phage), lack of standardized regulatory regimes at this time, phagic attack of the immune system etc. These types of studies need stronger and more in-depth research given the small scales and the short-term follow-ups. Some of these limitations have been addressed by new advances in phage engineering such as CRISPR modified phages and the development of better delivery vectors.

Economic assessments of phage therapy are also necessary since the upfront costs might be more than the standard antibiotics. The economic assessment also shows it could result in potential cost savings of up to 30 percent in the treatment of resistant infections but increased production is an obstacle. However, its ability to prevent costly complications related to treatment failure and to reduce burden of

antibiotic resistance may yield long term economic benefits.

The current regulatory environment requires comprehensive reform to accommodate phage therapy. Simplified approval mechanisms, standardized production methodologies and harmonized global regulatory frameworks are essential prerequisites to ensure patient safety and promote its integration into clinical practice.

In conclusion, phage therapy emerges as a highly promising modality to address the antimicrobial resistance crisis. Its successful translation from promise to practice hinges on filling extant research gaps, optimizing treatment strategies and streamlining regulatory processes. By surmounting these challenges, phage therapy can evolve into a fundamental component of modern therapeutics providing a critical tool for managing multidrug-resistant pathogens and safeguarding public health.

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